

Supplementary Figure S10. *In vitro* mono-culture and competition assays of WT, $\Delta aceE$, $\Delta aceF$, and $\Delta pflA$ in M9 0.5% glucose after 20h. (A-B) Mono-culture competitive index scores were calculated as a ratio of endpoint culture to initial culture of test strains versus a PDH+/PFL+ $\Delta lacZ$ strain grown in separate culture tubes; $[(Target_{Endpoint}/\Delta lacZ_{Endpoint}) / (Target_{Initial}/\Delta lacZ_{Initial})]$. (C-D) Competitive index scores were calculated as a ratio of output versus input $[(Target_{Output}/\Delta lacZ_{Output}) / (Target_{Input}/\Delta lacZ_{Input})]$. Strains were co-inoculated with a PDH+/PFL+ $\Delta lacZ$ strain to determine the relative fitness of each test strain. Data for each experiment was obtained from 3 biological replicates.